

Maintainers and restorers for MS577 A CMS lines.^a Karnataka, India. 1992 wet season.

Genotype	CMS lines			
	Pushpa A	Mangala A	ES18 A	Intan Mutant A
Kumkum Kesari	PR	M	R	-
ARC11353	M	M	-	M
IPS15	PR	M	-	-
IPS16	PR	M	-	M
M102	M	M	-	-
Suweon 352	PR	-	-	PR
Basmati 370	PR	M	-	-
Netra	M	M	-	-
Nutshell	M	-	-	-
Manipur	PR	-	-	-
IET5657-33	PR	-	PR	PR
CSR107	PR	-	-	-
Mandya Vani	M	-	-	-
Mandya Vijaya	M	-	-	-
IESH1	R	-	R	-
CTH1	M	-	-	-
HWR30	R	PR	-	-
Taichung 65	M	PR	-	-
CTH 3 (Mukthi)	R	M	M	R
IET8050	M	-	-	-
IET2014	M	M	-	-
HB5	PR	-	PR	-
IET5656	M	M	M	-
HWR2	M	M	-	-
Pusa 702	-	M	-	M
Chamundi	-	M	M	-
IET7991	-	-	PR	-
M210	PR	M	PR	-
IET7191	-	-	-	-
Milyang 54	M	M	-	-
IET8050	M	M	-	-
Indrasan	-	M	-	-
Milyang 46	-	PR	-	-
Primala	-	M	-	-
Purple dwarf	-	M	-	-
IR26	-	PR	PR	-
IR36	M	-	M	-
IR42	PR	-	-	-
IR46	-	M	-	-
IR50	-	M	-	-
IR50-31	PR	M	M	-
IR52	PR	M	M	M
IR54	M	M	-	-
IR64	M	-	M	-
IR74	M	PR	-	-
IR2429-315	-	M	-	-
IR2729-105	-	M	-	-
IR2797-105	M	-	-	-
IR3429-350	PR	-	-	-
IR9761-19-1	-	M	PR	-
IR11418-15-2	-	M	PR	-
IR13146-45	PR	-	-	-
IR13249-30	M	M	M	M
IR15975	PR	-	-	-
IR18350-90	PR	M	M	-
IR21916	M	-	-	-
IR25867-29	PR	-	-	-
IR27315	M	-	-	-
IR28178-70	-	M	-	-
IR28237-31	PR	-	-	-
IR30864	-	M	M	-
IR31358-90	PR	-	-	-
IR35358-90	PR	-	-	-
IR54752-3-5-8	PR	M	-	-
V20 B	R	M	-	M

^aM = maintainer, where pollen fertility and spikelet fertility = 0%; PR = partial restorer, where pollen fertility and spikelet fertility = 1-80%; and R = restorer, where pollen fertility and spikelet fertility = 81-100%.

parents were grouped into restorers, partial restorers, and maintainers (see table).

Of the 65 genotypes tested, 5 were restorers, 28 partial restorers, and 32 maintainers. Kumkum Kesari, IESH1, HWR30, CTH3 (Mukthi), and V20 B were restorers.

A pollen parent sometimes behaved as a restorer for one CMS line and as a partial restorer or maintainer for another. This shows that marked cytoplasmic nuclear interaction exists and that expression of restorer genes varies with genetic background of the female parents. ■

Yield potential

Stability analysis of six medium-duration rice genotypes across different N levels

S. Geetha, A. P. M. Kirubakaran Soundararaj, S. Giridharan, S. Mohandas, T. M. Thiyagarajan, and B. Selvi, Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute (TNRRI), Aduthurai 621001, Tamil Nadu, India

We studied the adaptiveness and stability of medium-duration rice at 0, 75, 150, and 225 kg N/ha. Genotypes ADT38, CO 45, ADT90072, Vikramarya, ADT40, and ADT39 were raised in a split-plot design with four replications from Oct 1992 to Feb 1993. N levels, applied as urea in three splits, were in the main plots. The genotypes, transplanted at a spacing of 20 × 10 cm, were in the sub-plots.

Data on panicles/plant, grains/panicle, percent fertility, 100-grain weight, single-plant yield, and harvest index were collected for 10 plants per experimental unit. We used the means of those plants for stability analysis following the method of Eberhart and Russel (1966). Pooled analysis of variance showed significant differences among genotypes and N treatments for all characters. Genotype × N interaction was also significant for all characters but 100-grain weight.

Table 1. Stability parameters ($\bar{X}$, $\bar{b}_i$, and s^2d_i) of six traits.^a TNRRI, Tamil Nadu, India. 1992-93.

	Panicles/plant			Grains/panicle			Percent fertility		
	$\bar{X}$	$\bar{b}_i$	s^2d_i	$\bar{X}$	$\bar{b}_i$	s^2d_i	$\bar{X}$	$\bar{b}_i$	s^2d_i
ADT38	10.05	1.306	0.249**	41.88	0.03	4.197	64.39	2.92	5.67*
CO 45	8.43	0.496**	0.002	54.75	1.37	7.148*	59.51	0.89	1.21
AD90072	9.08	1.106	0.485**	64.68	0.26	6.835*	66.94	1.73	0.48
Vikramarya	7.45	0.89	0.838**	44.05	1.23	5.914*	54.63	0.20	0.25
ADT40	10.46	1.27	0.126	64.23	1.73	29.27**	69.00	1.42	0.31
ADT39	9.17	0.93	0.382**	68.78	1.37	22.79**	68.07	-0.75	9.11*

	100-grain weight			Single-plant yield			Harvest index		
	$\bar{X}$	$\bar{b}_i$	s^2d_i	$\bar{X}$	$\bar{b}_i$	s^2d_i	$\bar{X}$	$\bar{b}_i$	s^2d_i
ADT38	1.97	2.67	0.0004**	7.74	0.55	0.063	0.40	0.66	0.00009
CO 45	2.34	0.40*	0.000	9.64	0.49	0.002	0.36	1.94**	0.00003
AD90072	1.97	0.61	0.0005**	10.08	1.02	0.202*	0.40	1.64	0.00004
Vikramarya	2.60	1.03	0.0000	9.14	1.03	1.690**	0.36	1.37	0.00020*
ADT40	2.25	0.49	0.000	13.29	1.76	0.645**	0.34	0.15	0.00020
ADT39	1.68	0.80	0.0000	10.42	1.15	0.387**	0.49	0.25*	0.00000

** and * = significant at the 1 and 5% level, respectively.

Table 2. Correlation among stability parameters ($\bar{X}$, $\bar{b}_i$, and s^2d_i).^a

	$\bar{X}$ vs $\bar{b}_i$	$\bar{X}$ vs s^2d_i	$\bar{b}_i$ vs s^2d_i
Panicles/plant	0.717	-0.603	0.096
Grains/panicle	0.379	0.701	0.684
Percent fertility	0.256	0.371	-0.204
100-grain weight	-0.208	-0.388	0.475
Single-plant yield	0.880*	0.095	0.395
Harvest index	-0.340	-0.702	-0.224

** = significant at the 5% level.

ADT38 and CO 45 were adaptive and stable across all N levels for single-plant yield. Mean single-plant yield was low for ADT38 and average for CO 45. The stable yield was due to stable grains/panicle and harvest index for ADT38 and panicles/plant and 100-grain weight for CO 45. Although the mean of ADT40 was high, its yield was unstable across the N levels (Table 1).

The correlation analysis among stability parameters revealed that genotypes with a high mean for single-plant yield are responsive to high N (Table 2). There was no significant association between the stability parameters of regression coefficient $\bar{b}_i$ and deviation from regression coefficient s^2d_i . It can be inferred that these two characters are not linked and are inherited separately. ■

Relationship of amylase activity to rice seedling growth at various greenhouse temperatures

Wang Sagen, Agronomy Department, Southwest Agricultural University, Chongqing 630716, China

Amylases are key enzymes for starch catabolism during rice seed germination. Higher amylase activity in kernels should enhance seedling vigor. This is important where seedlings are raised indoors before ambient temperatures are warm enough for rice growth. Temperature needs to be controlled carefully in greenhouse nurseries so that seedlings can better resist

stress after transplanting.

Seeds of hybrids Shanyou 63 and D-you 63 and conventional varieties Lushuang 1011 and Fujiang 2 were surface-sterilized and rinsed in sterile water. Seeds were then immersed in water for 2-3 d (depending on temperature), incubated for a day, and sown in a nutrient solution at different greenhouse temperatures.

Seedling characters and amylase activity were determined at 7 d after sowing (Table 1). Total amylase activity in kernels and dry weight of seedlings were assayed daily. Seeds were separated from shoots and roots when measuring shoot dry weight. Extracted kernel enzyme solution was incubated with

Table 1. Effects of different temperatures on seedling characters.^a

Temperature (°C)	Seedling height (cm)			Dry weight (mg/plant)			Root/shoot	Total amylase activity (µg maltose/kernel per s)
	Mean	±	sd	Mean	±	sd		
20	4.84		0.03 d	4.45	0.03 d		0.635 a	84.0 c
25	7.88		0.15 c	7.82	0.05 c		0.464 cd	188.4 a
30	13.97		0.23 a	10.32	0.23 a		0.406 d	179.3 ab
35	10.02		0.52 b	8.16	0.14 bc		0.481 c	121.4 bc
40	0.79		0.01 e	0.85	0.04 e		-	45.5 c
30/20	8.50		0.12 bc	8.04	0.15 bc		0.499 c	152.0 ab
30/25	9.15		0.27 bc	9.52	0.26 ab		0.509 bc	137.0 b
35→20 ^b	9.64		0.21 bc	10.91	0.31 a		0.554 b	165.0 ab

^a60 plants for each sample. Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bChange in temperature treatment.

IRRN REMINDER

Routine research. Reports of screening trials of varieties, fertilizer, cropping methods, and other routine observations using standard methodologies to establish local recommendations are not ordinarily accepted. Examples are single-season, single-trial field experiments. Field trials should be repeated across more than one season, in multiple seasons, or in more than one location as appropriate. All experiments should include replications and an internationally known check or control treatment.